

E-ISSN: 2583-9667

Indexed Journal

Peer Reviewed Journal

<https://multiresearchjournal.theviews.in>

Received: 21-10-2023

Accepted: 30-11-2023

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF ADVANCE RESEARCH IN MULTIDISCIPLINARY

Volume 1; Issue 2; 2023; Page No. 323-326

Dr. B.R. Ambedkar's contribution to the Dalit Women's Empowerment

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13284597>

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Abstract

The present article investigates the Indian economist, philosopher, humanitarian, law minister and father of the Indian constitution, Dr. B. R Ambedkar's ethical contribution to the empowerment of Dalit women in social, economic, educational, domestic and public gender equality order to uplift them to get the equal opportunities with men. The paper also brings out the struggles of Dalit women in the patriarchal system and hegemony of upper caste people to obtain freedom, individuality, constitutional provisions, economic status, cultural identification and self-employment in their living regions, especially resolve the economic, social and educational imbalances, the rural areas with lack of opportunities under the supremacy of upper caste their male-dominated society. Therefore, Babasaheb Ambedkar has struggled with women's equality and empowerment in Indian society how he endeavoured to provide equal wages when he was in the Bombay Legislative Assembly.

Keywords: Self-employment, economic status, empowerment, patriarchy, individual identity

Introduction

The research attempts to explore the contribution of Dr. B.R Ambedkar on Dalit empowerment collecting and referring the secondary sources of articles and books from journals, websites and libraries. Babasaheb Ambedkar is one of the first feminist leaders as well as the first women's rights advocates in the country. He has struggled for the empowerment of Dalit women Because the upper caste people have collapsed his community without getting proper respect. They dominate them with their talent, but the culturally constructed society is a big task that he has faced to answer. He has contributed immensely to the emancipation, empowerment and liberation of women from the clutches of religion, caste, class and patriarchal society under his mission as the social stratification based on a hierarchy of caste governs the social order. Says Ambedkar's social morality and vision make a casteless society and equality. There is no social freedom for Dalit women as well, and they are unable to get rights from their husbands as patriarchy, and Dalit women are not allowed to live independently in the male-dominated world. In asserting the importance of women in society, Ambedkar has outstripped his contemporaries who are engaged in nationalist movements or communal politics. He attempts to

involve women in all his programs and motivates them to enjoy the true freedom of individuals and lay equal opportunities for each (Poonam Singh, 2020) ^[10]. He issues many kinds of bills for Dalit women's empowerment and endeavours to show the right path for Dalit women by strong and special provisions. He created opportunities for Dalit women through his views on how to come out from Child marriage getting educational rights because they are unable to obtain education in the ethnarchy system's enforcement.

The Dalit women do not have a good education in front of the domination of upper caste people's rules and regulations. However, when Dr. B. R. Ambedkar became educated, he made them gain equal rights in obtaining education, empowering them in all other dire circumstances. Therefore, many Dalit women have been inspired by him to fight against the upper caste educated people when Savitribai Pule is ready to take education to come out of the problems and challenges. However, it has yet as a problem that women should be entitled to equal status with men, and they must have the right to education. Gender equality, gender mainstreaming, networking, leadership and financial freedoms are the essential aspects of women's empowerment, as Dr. Ambedkar has realised and included

in the process of social reforms. (Vaishali Dhanvijay 2012)
^[15] Dr. Ambedkar intends to help them in a manner way like what type of help is needed by him is helpful to the Dalit women to empowerment in society. She has been controlled by male-dominated being a doll for their hands.

He faced poverty along with a lack of administrative power by the time Dr. B. R. Ambedkar gave them the freedom to fly, and he became a tool in reducing the number of working hours and improving the working conditions. He has struggled to support a bill granting paid-for maternity leave to women working in factories. The Dalit women struggle on behalf of the superior caste and how they are not being avoided and do the work for free as ordinary people in a particular society purely based on caste, gender, power, ethnical, and education to control them. Hence, they are very lazy in backward people. It is so horrible to accept, but at the same time, there were no rights to make statements for Dalits, especially women. They feel shame wearing filthy clothes and having dirty lifestyles because gender equalities are enjoyed by seeing. The public has decided that they are useless and they should serve us a cup of rice. What kind of society?

Ambedkar's Contribution to the Women's Rights

He has contributed tremendous things to women's rights, especially to uplifting Dalit women. He has granted women the right to divorce, the right to inheritance and legal recognition of inter-caste marriages. Even for their empowerment, he adds many rights like speaking, voting, working and equality. He frames many laws for women in India viz, (i) Dearness Allowance, (ii) Employees' State Insurance, (iii) Provident Fund Act, (iv) Women Labour Welfare Fund, (v) Divorce Act, (vi) Right over parental Property, (vii) Women Labour Protection Act, (viii) Maternity benefit for women Labour bill, (ix) Leave Benefit to Piece Workers, (x) Revision of scale of pay for employees, Restoration of ban on women working underground in mines. (xii) No marriage before the age of 18 years, (xiii). The maintain allowance from the husband on getting a legal separation, (xiv) Widow can adopt a child (xv), Equal for equal work irrespective of the sex, and (xvi) Mother can change guardian of a minor by will. (Bindia Rani 2018) ^[6].

The Bill could not be introduced in its original structure as devised by Dr. Ambedkar and is enacted in a diluted version in four separate acts, namely the Hindu Marriage Act, 1955, Hindu Succession Act, 1956, Hindu Adoption and Maintenance 1956 and Hindu Minority and Guardianship 1956. Dr. Ambedkar's ideas have influenced the enactment of a number of subsequent pro-women Acts, such as The Child Marriage Restraint Act of 1929, Immoral Traffic (Prevention) Act 1956, Dowry Prohibition Act 1961, The Maternity Benefit Act 1961, The Equal Remuneration Act 1976, the Family Courts Act 1984, the Sati Prevention 1987, The National Commission -Women Act 1990. Protection of Human Rights Act 1993, Protection of Women from Domestic Violence 2005 (Shivam Prakash, 2019) ^[5].

Many people and philosophers have struggled for the freedom and empowerment of Dalit women. However, Dr. B.R. Ambedkar has done an excellent job for them, giving them several rights to survive independently. He tries to help them through justice and human rights. After the

existence of the British in India, the social activities protested dominance on struggles for untouchable women's education, child marriage, remarriage, Sathi system, educational rights and ignored women Pune in order to fulfil the wishes of refused educational rights and property rights in society. Moreover, Britain and America gave voting rights to women in 1918 and 1920, respectively. In the same way, MaDr.as City Council, Bihar and Odessa have given voting rights to women because Ambedkar had made a law for them. The writer Chitra Sawant, in the article "Women Should Understand Dr. Ambedkar's Teachings" (2019), identifies the views of Dr. BZ Khobragade on Ambedkar's influences on women empowerment: "In India, there are two types of woman empowerment moments, the one for the privileged classes, influenced totally by the western countries, whereas the other movement is being carried out by Dalit and Adivasi women i.e. Labourers, workers etc, for their rights and justice. However, unfortunately, the privileged class women's movement has not yet finally imbibed the thoughts of Dr. Ambedkar" (02). Moreover, the political thinker Dr. Ambedkar also looks at women empowerment in the Hindu Code Bill; he gives special allowance to women, as Poonam Singh explores in her article, "In his quest to ensure freedom, equality and individuality of Indian women, he resorted to the legalised mechanism and proposed sweeping constitutional provisions, famous as the Hindu code Bill, placing women at par with men in matters of inheritance and allowing them freedom to marry outside their caste" (17). Each abbreviation speaks of his struggle to provide human rights for women.

He mainly focuses on the social values of democracy, dignity and fraternity in his newspaper, Mook Nayak, to depict economic conditions and equal aspects of women when it comes to universal human rights. Even the scholar Dr. Karnika Dubey, in his article "Dr. B.R Ambedkar and Women Empowerment" (2020) ^[3], different layers of empowerment of women in Ambedkar's contribution "In several fields, including health, education, economic opportunities, gender-based violence, and political engagement; policies on women's empowerment exist at the national, state, and local (Panchayat) level" (10826). Furthermore, the writer illustrates Ambedkar's contribution to the development of women, especially Dalit women in India, as The signified period in which women can be referred to be signified for serving their assumption since the Vedic period, men dominated and enslaved them. According to Kumari (2020) ^[2], inhumanity, barbarism, child marriage, sati system, injustice, polygamy, illiteracy among women, sati system, and discrimination on sex, creed and caste system can be assumed as moral behaviour to be identified by society as rampant for women can be signified. It can be assumed in the Muslim religion that they can be sponsored for signifying the strict rules initiated for the women to stay in Parda and maintain the Parda system (Athwale, 2016) ^[17]. (10828), Dalit women struggle in the patriarchal system and hegemony of upper caste people to obtain freedom, individuality, constitutional provisions, economic status, cultural identification and self-employment in their living regions, especially to resolve the economic, social and educational imbalances in the rural areas with lack of opportunities under the supremacy of upper caste

and their male-dominated society. Because they have been discriminated by the upper caste as well as in their families' male domination. It is important to discuss women's status and Ambedkar's moral encouragement for women's conditions to live equal to men. The scholar Dr. Shreekrishna Tripathi, in the article "A Study of Dr. Bhimrao Ambedkar's Approach towards Women Empowerments" (2017) ^[12], Dr. B. R. Ambedkar's fight against the upper caste and Dalit patriarchy to facilitate women to survive independently "the content of all issues used to be on gender equality, women education and exposed the problems related to women and other depressed class. He studied the Hindu Shastras and Smritis extensively to find out the root cause of the degraded status of women in India. He strongly advocates for family planning measures for women in the Bombay Legislative Assembly" (56). In the same way, the scholar Shivam Prakash, in his article "Ambedkar's Contribution to the Empowerment of Women Were Remarkable" (2019) ^[5] displays Ambedkar as a champion in the subject of women's liberation and providing women's rights through the Indian constitution because he knows she has undergone many difficulties in her personal and public life. Therefore, the writer delves with an abbreviation in the article "The principal features of the Hindu Code Bill illustrate Dr. Ambedkar's passion towards the very values of liberty, equality, dignity and fraternity. It was a reform, challenging the basic patriarchal foundation to ensure equality of women, true to its essence of empowerment" (02). Of course, still, the patriarchal society still dominates women without proper awareness of the constitution. Even the lawyers, judges, and educated citizens do the same in their families on women. It is a question of identity for women. Significantly, Dalit women are double suppressed from society and within family members, but Ambedkar's legal legislation and acts helped them come into the mainstream among men and women.

Babasaheb Ambedkar has struggled for women's equality and empowerment in Indian society how he endeavoured to provide equal wages when he was in the Bombay Legislative Assembly. When he was a law minister, he specifically focused on Dalit women's education and their empowerment by giving them equal rights to utilise their property. Several writers have interpreted his tremendous contribution to them as the scholar Bindia Rani in her article "Dr. B.R. Ambedkar Thoughts and Contribution towards Women Empowerment" (2018) ^[6] how he struggles while structuring the constitution for all genders and castes equally as "He raised his voice against the Hindu social order and social system through renowned journal Mook Nayak in 1920 and Bahishkrit Bharat in 1927. Dr. Ambedkar raised many issues, including gender equality and women's and exposed the social, traditional and cultural problems faced by the women and other depressed classes in India" (28). Before, several social activists fought for social justice for all human beings in India, but Dr. B.R. Ambedkar attempted to provide equal rights within the structure of the legal constitution. That is the reason why, after his also throughout the world, commemorate him in their life. Therefore, the writer Amia Pisharody, in the article "Babasaheb Ambedkar: Champion of Women's Rights" (2020) ^[4], discloses Dr. B. R. Ambedkar not only worked for women he also stands with them to protect from

social hierarchies as "Ambedkar did not only right for women's rights, but he also continuously worked with women to realise the ambition of equality amongst genders. He advocated for the rights of sex workers and spoke out against the cattiest nature that was the foundation of sex work. He worked to ensure that women were also protected under labour laws" (02). Moreover, one of the scholars, Ms Pooja Kapoor, in her article "Women Empowerment", highlights the empowerment of female society in the below in her abbreviation: Empowerment denotes increasing the social, political, spiritual or economic forte of people and societies. Empowerment and self-sufficiency of women in the sphere of their economic, social, political and health status in both an extremely imperative end and compulsory for the accomplishment of sustainable human development¹. It is a multi-dimensional, multi-faceted, and manifold concept. (31). Whenever International Women's Day is celebrated, people at least remember Ambedkar's concern for the empowerment of women, especially in India. Being a Dalit, he faces several problems, but he does not leave other Dalits and women to struggle with the same condition; he fights for equal rights while preparing the Indian constitution. Dr. B. R. Ambedkar and, Savitribai Phule, Mahatma Jotiba Phule, worked much for women's education and their development in the domestic and public spheres. The article "Dr. B.R. Ambedkar and International Women's Day," his kind concern on maternity leave and their health condition as "Dr. B.R. Ambedkar raised the women's issue as Member of Legislative Council during his debate in the Bombay Legislative Assembly on 10 Noy, 1938; he strongly advocated family planning measures and said that besides many other problems giving birth to many chilDr.en negatively affects Mother's health" (03). He resigned from his minister position when the government declined to provide the proper rights for women, especially the Purdah system of Muslim women, as the scholar Dr. M.R. Singariva in the article "Dr. B R. Ambedkar and Women Empowerment in India" (2014) ^[9] about the secularist perspectives of Babasaheb "In turn, Dr., Ambedkar resigned from the cabinet expressing his discontent over non-acceptance of woman's right by the parliament. Besides, he highlighted the issues of Muslim women. His secular perspective is known through his thoughts on the "Purdah" (veil) system, religious conversations and legal rights for Muslim women. In short, along with the depressed class women, his thoughts for the emancipation of all the women are expressed with same allegiance" (02). Thus, many of the writings examine his contribution to Indian citizens to get an equal lifestyle. If the SC/STs forget Ambedkar, women should not forget him because he has struggled a lot for them questioning the entire societal system. He is the only person, who struggles for women to provide equal rights with men. Before, there were many social activists and reformists have been fighting for women's education and lifestyle and against the inadequate social systems for women. However, Ambedkar gives provisions within the structure Indian constitution legally. That is the reason many writers and scholars still commemorate him in their writings and during the celebrations; more specifically, they follow his philosophies regarding the secularistic life.

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